

WP6 Report of the Climate Litigation Survey

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1. Introduction

As part of Work Package 6 (WP6) of the Horizon Europe project *HRJust (States' Practice of Human Rights Justification: A Study in Civil Society Engagement and Human Rights Through the Lens of Gender and Intersectionality)*, we aim to better understand how states use human rights justifications (HRJs) in their responses to climate change. This involves identifying patterns in legal reasoning, considering gender and intersectional aspects, and exploring the links between climate policy, human rights, and international trade.

To support this research, a team from the World Trade Institute at the University of Bern and the Institute of International Relations in Prague conducted 43 semi-structured interviews between April and August 2024 with various stakeholders, including policymakers, legal experts, civil society representatives, and academics. The aim was to explore how HRJs are used in practice, what roles they play, and what challenges and opportunities they present.¹

After transcription and coding of the interviews using qualitative data analysis software Atlas.ti, recurring themes and common observations were identified. These served as the basis for a survey aimed at validating preliminary findings and gathering additional feedback. The results from the survey will contribute to inform the final stage of the WP6 Climate ODCSE Methodology, namely the co-production of knowledge.²

The survey was distributed via email to selected participants between March and April 2025. It included several preliminary conclusions drawn from the interview data. Respondents were invited to indicate whether they agreed with the presented findings and were also encouraged to share comments, clarify points, or add insights we might have missed. This step allows us to deepen our understanding and strengthen the accuracy and relevance of our research findings.

Before second the research survey to selected participants, Dr Cristani (IIR) completed the relevant ethic clearances, together with GDPR assessments, and acquired the necessary positive valuations on the "Climate Litigation Survey", "Ethics, GDPR And Research Survey. Guide on how to comply to the research ethics and personal data protection rules while conducting surveys in the framework of the HR project

¹ See the relevant report: Lukešová, B., Heepen, R., Němec, E. N., Ditrichová, P., & Cristani, F. (2025). WP6 Climate Interviews Report. In *HRJust WP6 Climate Working Paper Series*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1689462>.

² For the ODCSE Methodology implemented in WP6, see Cristani, F., Heepen, R., Lukešová, B., Němec, E. N., Ditrichová, P., Lhotský, J., & Bílková, V. (2025). Systematic Ongoing Direct Civil Society Engagement (ODCSE). WP6 Report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15773156>.

States' Practice of Human Rights Justification: A Study in Civil Society Engagement and Human Rights Through the Lens of Gender and Intersectionality (HRJust)" and "Participation in the Research Survey. Information Letter and Informed Consent Form" from the IIR Ethical Committee for Research and by the IIR contact person on personal data.³

2. Participants of the Survey

The survey was distributed to a selected group of participants, consisting of two main categories. The first group included respondents who had previously participated in the semi-structured interviews. These individuals were given the opportunity to react to the preliminary findings and provide additional reflections, clarifications, or critical feedback. This step was crucial for ensuring that our analysis accurately reflected their perspectives and captured nuances that may not have fully emerged during the interviews. The second group was composed of individuals who are involved in other activities organised within the HRJust project. We assumed that the survey topic would be of interest to them based on their involvement in other HRJust activities, and their responses later brought a variety of perspectives to the analysis.

The identification of selected participants (86 overall) was further guided by the following principles:

- *Domestic & International Qualifications Balance*: The sample included both national and EU-level policy officers, as well as judges from domestic and European judicial bodies. The same balanced approach was applied to the selection of civil society organizations;
- *Geographical Balance*: Interviewees were chosen from diverse regions worldwide. Within Europe, participants were selected from both smaller and larger Member States to capture varying geopolitical perspectives.
- *Thematic Balance*: Stakeholders were selected from different policy areas, including foreign affairs, environment, ministerial agencies, and local municipalities. Judicial authorities from both common law and civil law traditions were included, along with associations covering a broad range of interests related to climate change issues.
- *Familiarity with HRJust activities*: around 28% of the selected participants are former interviewees; all of them are already familiar with HRJust activities (from participating in

³ All original documents are on file with Dr Cristani (IIR) and duly archived at IIR premises.

previous civil society engagement activities or attending previous webinars or events organized within the project's activities)

After having identified the selected participants, a tracking document was established to monitor response progress. All relevant consent forms were duly filled in – currently archived at IIR premises (and on file with Dr Cristani, IIR). All research survey replies were then anonymized.

3. Content of the Survey

At the beginning of the survey, participants were introduced to the HRJust project, its objectives, and the fieldwork activities that led to the creation of the survey questions.

The survey consists of 12 questions, each introduced with a conclusion drawn from the interviews conducted during the HRJust project. After presenting each conclusion, participants were asked whether they agreed or disagreed with the statement by choosing a "Yes/No" response. Following this, participants had the opportunity to provide additional comments or elaborate on their answers in an open space provided after each question.

The following questions were included in the survey (The research survey form that was distributed is also reproduced in Annex I to this Report):

1. *To the question "Which human rights are the most affected by climate change?", answers include:*
 - *Right to life - 69%;*
 - *Right to healthy environment - 50%;*
 - *Right to health - 47%;*
 - *More generally, all human rights are impacted by climate change, because climate change affects humanity itself - 13%.*
2. *To the question "What are the state's positive obligations in this relation?", the most common answers include:*
 - *States have a positive obligation to take proactive actions to prevent, mitigate, and remedy the negative impacts of climate change on human rights;*
 - *States must take adaptation measures to ensure that populations, especially vulnerable ones, can adjust to the impacts of climate change;*
 - *States must provide transparency in their actions, show pathways to meeting their climate obligations (e.g., under the Paris Agreement), and demonstrate their efforts to mitigate climate impacts and meet human rights standards.*

3. To the question “Which vulnerable groups are the most affected by climate change?” answers include:
 - Low-income individuals - 54%;
 - Children - 51%;
 - Women - 49%;
 - Indigenous peoples - 46%.
4. To the question “What are the most effective instruments in terms of climate regulation, whether those adopted at international or at national level?”, the majority of answers point out that international level is more effective, as climate agenda has no boundaries, and thus it cannot be effectively regulated at national level only.
5. To the question “What are the most effective instruments in terms of climate litigation, whether those adopted at international or at national level?”, the majority of answers highlight that the effectiveness of international instruments largely depends on the specific jurisdiction. Some countries have highly effective mechanisms and a favorable political environment, while in others, due to the political situation and the lack of such mechanisms, it is more effective to argue using international instruments.
6. To the question “What are the most effective instruments in terms of climate litigation”, answers most frequently include the Paris Agreement, the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change or conventions protecting Indigenous Peoples (ILO Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention No. 169 or UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples).
7. To the question “To what extent do you find The Paris Agreement efficient and arguing with The Paris Agreement in climate litigation helpful?”, the majority of answers state the Paris Agreement serves as a key starting point for climate arguments, with many legal and political texts referencing it, but lacks specific obligations for the states and effective enforcement system.
8. To the question “What are the advantages of using human rights arguments during climate litigations?”, the majority of answers are affirmative; at the same time, they highlight also related challenges, as some human rights may be violated, some may collide etc. Accordingly, they highlight that it is important to conduct a proportionality test in these instances.
9. To the question “What do you think are the current barriers and obstacles that we see in the climate litigation context?”, the most frequent answers are lack of access to justice and lack of resources.
10. To question “What justifications do States use in order to defend their position?”, the majority of answers refer to the fact that States most frequently use the argument of separation of powers, arguing that this is not a matter for the courts to decide but a political question.
11. When asked about civil society engagement in climate policies, answers tend to agree that while civil society does not always get the space to engage, when they do, their involvement is highly beneficial, as they help represent vulnerable groups, provide accurate data and facilitate dialogue.
12. When asked about civil society engagement in climate litigation, most of the answers agree that it brings multiple advantages — providing legal expertise, funding, while also enhancing case credibility and media attention, though access to justice remains a challenge.

4. Drawing of conclusions and final observations

The survey was distributed to a total of 86 targeted stakeholders. The present data analysis is based on replies received until 30 April from 21 participants, thus 24% of the targeted people (14 from civil society representatives; 2 from judicial authorities, and 5 policy officers), 12 of whom were from the participants of the original interviews.

Though, generally, a good survey response rate often depends on factors like survey type, target audience, and distribution channel, a response rate of 20-25% is considered acceptable for online surveys and already enough to draw some conclusions.⁴ In this specific case, we had been quite selective in sharing the survey, targeting experienced stakeholders who could give meaningful insights on the topics at hand.

4.1. Results⁵

The survey responses show that the level of agreement with the presented conclusions varied across different questions. In most cases, a significant majority of participants agreed with the findings, though the percentage of agreement differed depending on the topic. Full consensus (100%) was achieved on the question concerning the use of human rights arguments in climate litigation (Q8). The highest levels of agreement thereafter were observed in relation to the relevance of the Paris Agreement (Q7), and the question addressing states' positive obligations, which garnered a 95% consensus. In other areas, such as the effectiveness of certain instruments in climate litigation (Q6), opinions were more divided, with a noticeable proportion of participants either partly agreeing or choosing not to answer.

QUESTION	YES	NO	PARTLY AGREE	NO ANSWER
Q1	81%	9,5%	4,8%	4,8%
Q2	95,2%	X	X	4,8%
Q3	66,7%	9,5%	9,5%	14,3%
Q4	62%	23,8%	9,5%	4,8%

⁴ Kinga Edwards, What is a Good Response Rate for a Survey?, SurveyLab, (6 June 2025), <https://www.surveylab.com/blog/what-is-a-good-response-rate-for-a-survey/#:~:text=A%20good%20survey%20response%20rate,between%2010%25%20and%2030%25.>

⁵ The following analysis is based on the data collected. The relevant datasets are available at Lukešová, B., & Cristani, F. (2025). WP6 Climate Litigation Survey Dataset. Statistical Data [Data set]. [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15730790> and Lukešová, B., & Cristani, F. (2025). WP6 Climate Litigation Survey Dataset. Comments from Participants [Data set]. [Data set] [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15730831>.

Q5	85,7%	4,8%	4,8%	4,8%
Q6	38,1%	19%	14,2%	28,6%
Q7	95,2%	X	X	4,8%
Q8	100%	X	X	X
Q9	71,4%	19%	9,5%	X
Q10	57,1%	14,3%	9,5%	19%
Q11	90,5%	X	4,8%	4,8%
Q12	90,5%	X	4,8%	4,8%

Table 1. Table showing the statistical results of the Climate Litigation Survey

4.2. Comments⁶

Participants engaged actively with the survey, providing a range of valuable comments across all questions. The highest number of comments was received for Questions 1 (Which human rights are the most affected by climate change), 3 (Which vulnerable groups are the most affected by climate change?), and 6 (What are the most effective instruments in terms of climate litigation), which each presented specific answer options based on the preliminary findings. These questions appeared to prompt more detailed reflections and critical engagement from respondents.

Question 6 (What are the most effective instruments in terms of climate litigation), in particular, generated notable discussion and showed the highest level of disagreement among participants. Unlike most other questions, where a strong majority agreed with the presented findings, the responses to Question 6 were more divided, and a significant number of participants either partly agreed or provided critical comments.

Overall, the participants' comments helped to improve the analysis by bringing new perspectives, suggesting additional points to consider, and showing where the preliminary findings could be developed further.

4.3. Comments to the Single Questions

4.3.1. Question 1 (Which human rights are the most affected by climate change)

To the question "Which human rights are the most affected by climate change?", answers include:

- Right to life - 69%;
- Right to healthy environment - 50%;

⁶ The following analysis is based on the data collected: Lukešová, B., & Cristani, F. (2025). WP6 Climate Litigation Survey Dataset. Comments from Participants [Data set]. [Data set] [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15730831>.

- Right to health - 47%;
- More generally, all human rights are impacted by climate change, because climate change affects humanity itself - 13%.

Figure 1. Question 1: Statistical Results

The comments revealed a variety of perspectives that further developed the preliminary findings. Eight participants agreed that climate change impacts all human rights, emphasizing that it affects humanity as a whole rather than only specific rights. Several noted that this broader understanding should have been more prominent in the original results. One participant raised the possibility of an "attention bias," suggesting that the focus on the rights to life, health, and a healthy environment may reflect their prominence in international decisions rather than a full legal analysis of climate change impacts.⁷

Three participants stated that the right to a healthy environment is the most affected, considering other rights less central in this context.⁸ One participant emphasized that the right to life is most threatened, noting that climate change directly endangers human lives.⁹ Another found it interesting that many respondents prioritize the right to life over the right to a healthy environment, interpreting this as a perception of climate change as a greater threat to humanity than to nature itself.¹⁰ Some participants

⁷ Comment from Civil Society 3.

⁸ Comments from Civil Society 4, Policy Officer 3, and Civil Society 14.

⁹ Comment from Civil Society 1.

¹⁰ Comment from policy Officer 1.

also mentioned additional rights they considered heavily impacted by climate change, such as the right to private and family life, the right to property, the right to business, the right to food, water, and housing.

Finally, one comment stressed that all rights are affected, but the extent varies depending on the situation.¹¹ It was suggested that the categorization of impacted rights should better reflect their interconnections. Overall, the feedback largely confirmed the original conclusions while expanding the understanding of how broadly and deeply climate change affects human rights.

4.3.2. Question 2 (What are the state's positive obligations)

To the question “What are the state's positive obligations in this relation?”, the most common answers include:

- States have a positive obligation to take proactive actions to prevent, mitigate, and remedy the negative impacts of climate change on human rights;
- States must take adaptation measures to ensure that populations, especially vulnerable ones, can adjust to the impacts of climate change;
- States must provide transparency in their actions, show pathways to meeting their climate obligations (e.g., under the Paris Agreement), and demonstrate their efforts to mitigate climate impacts and meet human rights standards.

¹¹ Comment from Judicial Authority 1.

Figure 2. Question 2: Statistical Results

One of the participants emphasized that the obligations of states in relation to climate action and human rights are not merely declaratory or symbolic; these obligations must be understood as legally binding and subject to scrutiny, thereby reinforcing the responsibility of states to both act and be held accountable for the implementation of their commitments.¹² Importantly, participants underlined that transparency should not be narrowly interpreted as the publication of regular reports. Instead, transparency was framed as an ongoing participatory process, involving civil society and directly affected communities. This understanding aligns with a broader conception of participatory governance, where decision-making becomes more inclusive and democratic. Another key point raised was the inherently positive nature of state obligations. These are not limited to the negative duty to refrain from rights violations but also encompass affirmative duties to actively protect.

Participants also stressed the multi-level nature of these obligations. While national strategies play a crucial role in shaping climate action, recognition was given to the importance of local-level strategies and actions—including those undertaken by sub-national regions, municipalities, and cities. These local initiatives are often inspired by or aligned with national frameworks, but they also represent essential entry points for citizen participation, which tends to be more effective and meaningful at the local or regional scale. The issue of transparency was revisited in critical terms when discussing current European climate frameworks. For instance, the Green Deal Agreement was cited as an example of insufficiently clear communication, with some participants observing that its objectives and mechanisms remain ambiguous and open to varied interpretations. A strong consensus emerged around the necessity of adopting a human rights-based approach to climate policy. Such a framework not only provides legal grounding for state obligations but also ensures that the needs and rights of the most vulnerable populations are prioritized.

Concerning the sources of these obligations, participants pointed to a range of normative frameworks. Some referenced EU directives as important instruments shaping national climate responsibilities. Others highlighted the foundational role of international human rights law and international environmental law, noting that the positive obligations of states reflect the principles embedded in these legal regimes. In this context, the recent ruling of the European Court of Human Rights in the *KlimaSeniorinnen* case was cited as a compelling articulation of these duties, offering a concrete legal expression of how states must act to protect rights in the face of the climate crisis.

¹² Comment from Judicial Authority 1.

4.3.3. Question 3 (Which vulnerable groups are the most affected by climate change)

To the question "Which vulnerable groups are the most affected by climate change?" answers include:

- Low-income individuals - 54%;
- Children - 51%;
- Women - 49%;
- Indigenous peoples - 46%.

Figure 3. Question 3: Statistical Results

Many respondents emphasized that all vulnerable groups are at risk from the impacts of climate change. In addition to the most frequently mentioned groups—low-income individuals, children, women, and indigenous peoples—respondents also highlighted older people and those with disabilities or medical vulnerabilities, especially in the context of heatwaves, extreme weather events, and limited adaptive capacity. Further groups mentioned included workers in sectors undergoing transition due to climate policies (e.g., coal miners) and climate-displaced persons—those forced to relocate due to the climate crisis.¹³ Indigenous peoples were also highlighted as one of the most at-risk groups, with their unique cultural and environmental connections being emphasized as factors that make them particularly sensitive to environmental destruction.

¹³ Comments from Civil Society 2 and Judicial Authority 1.

Some participants also highlighted the importance of considering vulnerability through an intersectional lens. They noted that people who belong to multiple marginalized groups—such as low-income indigenous women—are at an even greater risk due to overlapping vulnerabilities and simultaneous discrimination. A few respondents noted that the effects of climate change are highly context-dependent. The vulnerability of different groups can vary significantly depending on the region, the local climate conditions, and whether individuals live in urban or rural areas.

Overall, the feedback confirmed the preliminary findings but suggested expanding the list of vulnerable groups and considering the complex, context-specific, and intersectional nature of vulnerability to climate change.

4.3.4. Question 4 (What are the most effective instruments in terms of climate regulation)

To the question “What are the most effective instruments in terms of climate regulation, whether those adopted at international or at national level?”, the majority of answers point out that international level is more effective, as climate agenda has no boundaries, and thus it cannot be effectively regulated at national level only.

Figure 4. Question 4: Statistical Results

Comments regarding this question provided by our respondents were largely in agreement. Many emphasized that the international level is more effective in addressing climate regulation, given that the climate agenda transcends national borders and therefore cannot be adequately tackled by national measures alone. Respondents highlighted that international frameworks are crucial to set the rules, provide coordination, and ensure a unified global response. At the same time, several limitations of this

level were noted: it is often seen as too weak, not legally binding, lacking enforcement mechanisms, and underfunded. In contrast, respondents consistently argued that the implementation of internationally agreed commitments must take place at the national level. States were described as playing a crucial role in translating international commitments into concrete action, including transposing agreements into national law, adapting measures to local conditions, and ensuring effective enforcement. A number of respondents summarized their position by calling for a balanced approach that integrates strong international commitment with robust national enforcement — or, in other words, a global system that allows for local implementation. One respondent also offered a nuanced view by expressing full agreement with the international focus in terms of mitigation, but pointing out that when it comes to adaptation, action must necessarily take place at the national level.¹⁴

4.3.5. Question 5 (Whether international or national instruments are the most effective in terms of climate litigation)

To the question “What are the most effective instruments in terms of climate litigation, whether those adopted at international or at national level?”, the majority of answers highlight that the effectiveness of international instruments largely depends on the specific jurisdiction. Some countries have highly effective mechanisms and a favorable political environment, while in others, due to the political situation and the lack of such mechanisms, it is more effective to argue using international instruments.

Figure 5. Question 5: Statistical Results

¹⁴ Comment from Policy Officer 1.

Our respondents provided a variety of comments that highlighted different dimensions of effectiveness. One participant pointed out that the answers often referred less to the effectiveness of the instruments themselves and more to the effectiveness of their application, which can differ significantly across contexts.¹⁵ Another respondent emphasized the distinction between developed and developing countries, noting that the institutional and political conditions shape the potential impact of litigation strategies.¹⁶ A further observation stressed that effectiveness depends on the interaction between national and international jurisdictions, as well as on the degree of justiciability of climate obligations within a given legal system.¹⁷ For some, adopting a dedicated climate law at the national level stood out as an effective tool, while others argued that both national and international instruments could deliver meaningful results if governments act transparently and impose binding obligations on states. One particularly interesting comment referred to the Arctic and Antarctica as examples where international governance appears more appropriate, since leaving these regions to competition among states would likely lead to destructive exploitation of resources.¹⁸

4.3.6. Question 6 (What are the most effective instruments in terms of climate litigation)

To the question “What are the most effective instruments in terms of climate litigation”, answers most frequently include the Paris Agreement, the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change or conventions protecting Indigenous Peoples (ILO Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention No. 169 or UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples).

¹⁵ Comment from Civil Society 2.

¹⁶ Comment from Civil Society 1.

¹⁷ Comment from Judicial Authority 1.

¹⁸ Comment from Civil Society 13.

Figure 6. Question 6: Statistical Results

Many participants acknowledge the significance of the Paris Agreement and the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), but they argue that, on their own, these instruments are not particularly effective in climate litigation due to their lack of binding obligations and enforceable sanctions. These agreements are generally regarded as frameworks for guiding state actions.

Many respondents highlighted the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) and, more broadly, human rights instruments (for example UN Covenant on Civil and Political Rights) as the most effective tools for climate litigation. They emphasized the growing role of human rights law in holding governments accountable for climate inaction, particularly concerning the right to life and a healthy environment. In addition, several participants pointed to the Aarhus Convention, which provides access to justice in environmental matters, and the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), as important legal frameworks that could support climate litigation. Several respondents emphasize the growing importance of human rights instruments in climate litigation.

National climate laws also feature prominently in the responses, with many asserting that these laws, which can set binding emission reduction targets, are crucial for holding states accountable. Court decisions, while not legally binding, are noted for their role in building precedents that can be referenced in future litigation. Another key point raised is the role of specialized conventions protecting indigenous peoples, such as the ILO Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention No. 169 and the UN

Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, which have been successfully applied in cases involving deforestation and protection of traditional territories.

Overall, there is a consensus that no single instrument is fully sufficient for climate litigation. Instead, respondents emphasize the complementary nature of various instruments, combining international treaties, human rights laws, and national legislation

4.3.7. Question 7 (Using the Paris Agreement in climate litigation)

To the question “To what extent do you find The Paris Agreement efficient and arguing with The Paris Agreement in climate litigation helpful?”, the majority of answers state the Paris Agreement serves as a key starting point for climate arguments, with many legal and political texts referencing it, but lacks specific obligations for the states and effective enforcement system.

Figure 7. Question 7: Statistical Results

To this general finding, respondents largely agreed but offered a series of additional comments. One participant noted that one of the major limitations of the Paris Agreement is that the term “fossil fuels” does not appear anywhere in the document, which weakens its force as a climate instrument.¹⁹ Another underlined that interpretation of the Agreement may vary significantly between countries, as states remain free to choose their own approach to implementation.²⁰ In relation to litigation, a respondent emphasized that the Paris Agreement should be understood more as a persuasive argument than a

¹⁹ Comment from Civil Society 9.

²⁰ Comment from Civil Society 4.

coercive instrument, given its lack of binding obligations and enforcement mechanisms.²¹ One respondent raised the question of whether the frequent reliance on the Paris Agreement in litigation reflects its persuasive power, or whether it is simply the case that it is the last major international climate accord following the failure of Copenhagen (The Copenhagen Accord, adopted at the 2009 UN Climate Change Conference in Copenhagen (COP15)) and the inadequacies of the Kyoto Protocol.²² Another participant, reflecting on the withdrawal of some parties, suggested that it might be more feasible to amend international human rights conventions instead.

4.3.8. Question 8 (What are the advantages of using human rights arguments during climate litigations)

To the question “What are the advantages of using human rights arguments during climate litigations?”, the majority of answers are affirmative; at the same time, they highlight also related challenges, as some human rights may be violated, some may collide etc. Accordingly, they highlight that it is important to conduct a proportionality test in these instances.

Figure 8. Question 8: Statistical Results

Many participants agreed with the original formulation, noting that it accurately reflects both the advantages and the challenges of using human rights arguments in climate litigation. Several voices went further, stressing that human rights should be used more extensively in this context. Others pointed to the need for courts to adopt an intersectional perspective when dealing with climate cases,

²¹ Comment from Judicial Authority 1.
²² Comment from Civil Society 13.

as the climate crisis does not affect all groups equally. One participant emphasized that the climate crisis will intensify existing social inequalities, which must therefore be taken into account in all adaptation and mitigation measures.²³ Another underlined that the scope of argumentation should be broadened beyond the direct protection of individual rights to include the wider consequences of environmental degradation.²⁴ This encompasses not only immediate dangers to life and property from extreme climate events, but also the longer-term impacts on quality and security of life, such as forced migration, economic disruption, and potential conflicts over scarce resources.

4.3.9. Question 9 (Current barriers and obstacles in climate litigation)

To the question “What do you think are the current barriers and obstacles that we see in the climate litigation context?”, the most frequent answers are lack of access to justice and lack of resources.

Figure 9. Question 9: Statistical Results

Most participants agreed with the identification of lack of access to justice and lack of resources as central barriers in climate litigation, but they also expanded the discussion in several important directions. Some underlined that these barriers are closely connected to persistent social inequalities, which shape who can seek justice and under what conditions. Others pointed to institutional shortcomings, particularly the absence of clear mechanisms for holding states and corporations

²³ Comment from Civil Society 10.

²⁴ Comment from Civil Society 13.

accountable, the legal uncertainty surrounding the justiciability of climate obligations, and the high degree of dependence on how courts interpret these obligations.

Several participants stressed the need for procedural improvements, such as strengthening legal aid, enabling broader public interest litigation, and ensuring judicial independence. Others emphasized a more fundamental obstacle: the inexistence of a robust legal basis for climate action. Even when courts declare a human rights violation in connection with climate change, their judgments often lack clarity on how such breaches should be addressed. This challenge is compounded by the problem of weak enforcement and a lack of political will to implement climate-related court decisions.

In addition to these legal and political challenges, participants also pointed to informational barriers. The lack of widespread public knowledge about the worsening effects of climate change and pollution, as well as broader deficits in education, were seen as critical factors limiting the reach of climate litigation. Finally, one participant noted that the relative novelty of climate litigation should also be acknowledged.²⁵ By drawing a parallel with international investment arbitration, they reminded that it took decades after the adoption of the ICSID Convention before investment disputes became common, suggesting that climate litigation may similarly require time to develop into a mature legal practice.

4.3.10. Question 10 (What justifications do States use in order to defend their position)

To question “What justifications do States use in order to defend their position?”, the majority of answers refer to the fact that States most frequently use the argument of separation of powers, arguing that this is not a matter for the courts to decide but a political question.

²⁵ Comment from Civil Society 5.

Figure 10. Question 10: Statistical Results

In response to the question on what justifications States use to defend their positions, participants largely confirmed that the separation of powers argument is a frequent line of defence, with States maintaining that climate issues are political questions rather than judicial ones. At the same time, participants highlighted several additional arguments commonly invoked by States. Among them is the so-called “drop in the sea” argument, whereby States claim that their individual efforts are meaningless in the face of inaction by major emitters. Similarly, many States frame climate change as a global challenge requiring collective international action, insisting that imposing obligations on a single country would be unfair or ineffective without broader cooperation. Another used argument is that a State’s current level of climate action is already sufficient, particularly given the difficulty of quantifying with precision how much action is legally or scientifically required.

Economic justifications were also identified as central: States often argue that more drastic climate measures would entail significant negative consequences such as job losses, reduced industrial competitiveness, and broader economic instability, which must be weighed against environmental objectives. Another frequent strategy is to challenge the standing of plaintiffs, with States questioning whether individuals, NGOs, or groups have the necessary legal interest to bring a claim, or whether the claims themselves are too broad or speculative for judicial resolution. References to national interests and insufficient resources to carry out demanded measures were also mentioned as recurring justifications.

One participant stressed that although States appear to rely on a wide array of legal and practical arguments, their underlying motivations are primarily political.²⁶ Another participant, however, cautioned that the initial conclusion in this answer might be too harsh, reminding that States do not only deploy these justifications strategically but also challenge claims on substantive grounds that go to the merits of the case.²⁷

4.3.11. Question 11 (Civil society engagement in climate policies)

When asked about civil society engagement in climate policies, answers tend to agree that while civil society does not always get the space to engage, when they do, their involvement is highly beneficial, as they help represent vulnerable groups, provide accurate data and facilitate dialogue.

Figure 11. Question 11: Statistical Results

On the question of civil society engagement in climate policies, most participants reaffirmed the view that while civil society is not always given sufficient space to participate, its involvement is highly valuable whenever it occurs. Participants highlighted further benefits. Civil society organizations play an important role in raising public awareness and often step in where states are either unable or unwilling to act. Several participants emphasized the need for stronger financial support from public authorities to sustain civil society's contributions. Others suggested that civil society actors should also improve

²⁶ Comment from Policy Officer 2.

²⁷ Comment from Policy Officer 3.

their communication strategies, for instance by “marketing” their activities more effectively in order to gain visibility and influence.

At the same time, participants noted certain challenges. One pointed out that government-organized NGOs (GONGOs) can sometimes overshadow the work of independent organizations, undermining the authenticity of civil society input.²⁸

4.3.12. Question 12 (Civil society engagement in climate litigation)

When asked about civil society engagement in climate litigation, most of the answers agree that it brings multiple advantages — providing legal expertise, funding, while also enhancing case credibility and media attention, though access to justice remains a challenge.

Figure 12. Question 12: Statistical Results

Several participants provided comments on this part of our research, largely affirming the points raised while also adding their own perspectives. Some emphasized the importance of media attention, noting that it plays a crucial role in shaping broader awareness and responses. Others highlighted that access to justice is a highly regional and state-dependent issue, and one respondent even stressed that, in their view, civil society’s access to justice has generally worsened rather than improved in recent years. Participants also underlined the fact that civil society is more directly connected to people, including vulnerable groups, which gives it a distinctive position compared to other actors. One participant

²⁸ Comment from Civil Society 9.

remarked that such initiatives felt more meaningful than forms of activism like gluing oneself to the road or art-based interventions, suggesting that they saw greater value in these efforts.²⁹

Another participant reflected on the possibility that civil society engagement is not exclusively positive. Referring to existing literature, they highlighted critiques that portray NGO activity as one-sided activism and noted that in some contexts strong advocacy can also provoke counter-movements that work against climate policies.³⁰

²⁹ Comment from Civil Society 13.

³⁰ Comment from Civil Society 3.

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Annex I. Research Survey Form

CLIMATE LITIGATION SURVEY

Preliminary Results from the Fieldwork Activities on Climate Litigation within the HRJust project: A Research Survey

1. The Horizon Europe project HRJust (*States' Practice of Human Rights justification: A Study in Civil Society Engagement and Human Rights Through the Lens of Gender and Intersectionality*)³¹ aims to address significant and important gaps in human rights regulations and to develop a theory of human rights justifications. HRJust aims to develop a theory of HRJ and a process for Systematic Ongoing Civil Society Engagement as a tool for a gender and intersectional inclusive Civil Society Engagement. HRJust is to identify gaps in human rights regulations and protection, serving as underpinning data for our recommendations to the European Union (EU) in support of a multinational human rights system and promotion of transnational democratic governance. The HRJust project is coordinated by the University of Gothenburg (SE) and involves 15 partners, including the World Trade Institute of the University of Bern, Switzerland (UBERN) and the Institute of International Relations in Prague, Czechia (IIR). The HRJust project runs for 3 years (from 1 March 2023 to 28 February 2026).
2. WP6 of the HRJust project is tasked to map States' uses of Human Rights Justifications (HRJs) when responding to climate change, comparing/contrasting approaches of different legal regimes, understand the realities of the impacts of the measures related to climate change, identify new actors/new roles for existing actors, identify geopolitical elements and gender considerations and explore opportunities and challenges of new policy avenues when climate, human rights and international trade are considered together.
3. To carry out this part of the research, a team from the World Trade Institute of the University of Bern and the Institute of International Relations Prague have conducted 43 semi-structured interviews (between April and August 2024) with stakeholders to identify the role of HRJs, including their impacts, perceived challenges, and opportunities.

* Horizon Europe project HRJust (*States' Practice of Human Rights Justification: a study in civil society engagement and human rights through the lens of gender and intersectionality*), GA No. 101094346. This project has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

4. As we are in the process of analysing the data collected through our field work, we are reaching out to you to kindly ask for your feedback on our preliminary results of our empirical activity. Your answers will help us refine and advance further in our research.
5. We are thus inviting you to take a survey for research. The survey has been designed by the team from the World Trade Institute of the University of Bern (Prof. Elisa Fornalè, Ms Riccarda Heepen and Ms Felicia Meyer) and the Institute of International Relations Prague (Dr. Federica Cristani, Prof. Veronika Bílková, Ms Barbora Lukešová and Ms Magdalena Florová), who will then analyse the relevant results.
6. This survey is completely voluntary. There are no negative consequences if you don't want to take it. If you start the survey, you can always change your mind and stop at any time. You can also skip as many questions as you wish or quit the survey at any time.
7. This survey will take approximately 10 minutes to complete; 15-20 minutes if you wish to engage more in our feedback.

BACKGROUND INFORMATION: FIELDWORK ACTIVITIES

Within the framework of the HRJust project, a research team from the World Trade Institute of the University of Bern and the Institute of International Relations Prague have conducted 43 semi-structured interviews (between April and August 2024) with stakeholders to identify the role of human rights justifications in climate litigation, including their impacts, perceived challenges, and opportunities.

This way, the realities and impacts of human rights justifications were explored, as well as their interplay with key legal themes like jurisdiction, procedural limits, and extraterritoriality.

This empirical research employs the Systematic Ongoing Direct Civil Society Engagement (ODCSE) approach and prioritizes civil society participation in knowledge. Within this framework, the present survey aims to gather feedback from relevant participants in our preliminary result from the interviews that we conducted. The feedback that will we receive will help us in advancing in our research.

The interviews were conducted with policy officers (11), judicial authorities (11), and national and international associations (21). The interviewee selection took into consideration the balance of the background of the interviewees. Accordingly, both national policy officers as well as EU level officers were included in the groups. Parallely, the group of judges included domestic and European level judicial authorities as well. In order to ensure a balanced representation of civil society, the same consideration was given to the selection of the related associations as well. Interviewees were chosen from diverse geographical regions to ensure representation from various continents. Within the European context, a broad range of Member States, encompassing both smaller and larger states, were included. This approach aimed to observe and understand the different perceptions that emerge from these distinct geopolitical

entities. The interview design aims to ensure a thematic balance encompassing diverse stakeholders from different interest areas. Policy officers were selected from different ministries including ministry of foreign affairs and the environment, ministerial agencies, DGs of the European Commission and officers working in local municipalities. Judicial authorities were selected from various professional backgrounds and from both common law and civil law jurisdictions. The diversity of associations was also taken into account and associations covering a spectrum of areas were included in the research. A gender balance was also aimed to be ensured throughout the interviews. Out of 43 interviews, 25 are women and 18 men.

The interviews were semi-structured, i.e. they included pre-determined open questions. As informed by the theoretical framework established by the project, the aim of the interviews was to understand how states use Human Rights to justify and defend their actions and decisions. Accordingly, the questions were formulated to enable the researcher to identify firstly the non-private actors that justify their actions or decisions by way of using a human rights justification. In this context, researchers endeavored to identify the type of arguments. Accordingly, researchers tried to understand what kind of arguments non-private actors embrace, i.e. based on legal reasoning, national interest, security concerns or whether they are ethical, moral, value based etc. The questions were formulated to understand the function of law in terms of HR justifications and in what context HR Justifications are used.

RESEARCH SURVEY

The following questions are structured in two parts. The first one illustrates one key finding that emerged from the interviews conducted as mentioned above (all the data is presented in an anonymous and aggregated way); the second one aims to gather the feedback from the participant to the survey.

Thank you in advance for your time and participation!

1. To the question “Which human rights are the most affected by climate change?”, answers include:

- Right to life - 69%;
- Right to healthy environment - 50%;
- Right to health - 47%;
- More generally, all human rights are impacted by climate change, because climate change affects humanity itself - 13%.

Do you agree? (Y/N)

Would you like to comment?

2. To the question “What are the state's positive obligations in this relation?”, the most common answers include:

- States have a positive obligation to take proactive actions to prevent, mitigate, and remedy the negative impacts of climate change on human rights;
- States must take adaptation measures to ensure that populations, especially vulnerable ones, can adjust to the impacts of climate change;
- States must provide transparency in their actions, show pathways to meeting their climate obligations (e.g., under the Paris Agreement), and demonstrate their efforts to mitigate climate impacts and meet human rights standards.

Do you agree? (Y/N)

Would you like to comment?

3. To the question “Which vulnerable groups are the most affected by climate change?” answers include:

- Low-income individuals - 54%;
- Children - 51%;
- Women - 49%;
- Indigenous peoples - 46%.

Do you agree? (Y/N)

Would you like to comment?

4. To the question “What are the most effective instruments in terms of climate regulation, whether those adopted at international or at national level?”, the majority of answers point out that international level is more effective, as climate agenda has no boundaries, and thus it cannot be effectively regulated at national level only.

Do you agree? (Y/N)

Would you like to comment?

5. To the question “What are the most effective instruments in terms of climate litigation, whether those adopted at international or at national level?”, the majority of answers highlight that the effectiveness of international instruments largely depends on the specific jurisdiction. Some countries have highly effective mechanisms and a favorable political environment, while

in others, due to the political situation and the lack of such mechanisms, it is more effective to argue using international instruments.

Do you agree? (Y/N)

Would you like to comment?

6. To the question “What are the most effective instruments in terms of climate litigation”, answers most frequently include the Paris Agreement, the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change or conventions protecting Indigenous Peoples (ILO Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention No. 169 or UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples).

Do you agree? (Y/N)

Would you like to comment?

7. To the question “To what extent do you find The Paris Agreement efficient and arguing with The Paris Agreement in climate litigation helpful?”, the majority of answers state the Paris Agreement serves as a key starting point for climate arguments, with many legal and political texts referencing it, but lacks specific obligations for the states and effective enforcement system.

Do you agree? (Y/N)

Would you like to comment?

8. To the question “What are the advantages of using human rights arguments during climate litigations?”, the majority of answers are affirmative; at the same time, they highlight also related challenges, as some human rights may be violated, some may collide etc. Accordingly, they highlight that it is important to conduct a proportionality test in these instances.

Do you agree? (Y/N)

Would you like to comment?

9. To the question “What do you think are the current barriers and obstacles that we see in the climate litigation context?”, the most frequent answers are lack of access to justice and lack of resources.

Do you agree? (Y/N)

Would you like to comment?

10. To question “What justifications do States use in order to defend their position?”, the majority of answers refer to the fact that States most frequently use the argument of separation of powers, arguing that this is not a matter for the courts to decide but a political question.

Do you agree? (Y/N)

Would you like to comment?

11. When asked about civil society engagement in climate policies, answers tend to agree that while civil society does not always get the space to engage, when they do, their involvement is highly beneficial, as they help represent vulnerable groups, provide accurate data and facilitate dialogue.

Do you agree? (Y/N)

Would you like to comment?

12. When asked about civil society engagement in climate litigation, most of the answers agree that it brings multiple advantages — providing legal expertise, funding, while also enhancing case credibility and media attention, though access to justice remains a challenge.

Do you agree? (Y/N)

Would you like to comment?

